

Oxidation of Organic Selenides to Selenoxides with Thallium(III) Salts¹

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Thallium trinitrate oxidizes diaryl- and aryl alkyl- selenides to their corresponding selenoxides in good yields. Oxidation with thallium tris(trifluoroacetate) is also discussed.

TRIVALENT thallium[Th(III)] is a "soft acid"² which can react as an oxidizing agent.³ Its potential reactivity with organic selenium(II) compounds ("soft bases") is highly expected, but no examples for such reactions have been known. We report here the oxidation reaction of selenides to selenoxides by thallium trinitrate (TTN).

Up to date, several oxidizing agents, for instance, hydrogen peroxide⁴, ozone⁵, periodate⁶, *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid⁷, oxygen⁸ etc. have been used for oxidation of selenides to selenoxides. Now, TTN was shown to oxidize diaryl- and aryl alkyl- selenides to selenoxides easily at room temperature in very good yields. The results of the reaction are summarized in Table.

Aryl alkyl selenide (1a) was shown to be more easily oxidized than diaryl selenides, 1b and 1c. The electron-donating substituents on the *para*-positions of the diphenyl selenide accelerate the reaction. (Compare 1b to 1c in Table.) In every case, the formation of selenone was not observed, and isolation of selenoxide was very easy.

As the origin of oxygen for the formation of selenoxide, water of crystallisation in TTN or nitric acid (or nitrate anion) is considered, but discrimination is difficult.

The reaction of phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) with thallium tris(trifluoroacetate) (TTFA), which had no water of crystallisation, in trifluoroacetic acid under nitrogen did not produce the selenoxide (2a), but it gave diphenyl diselenide (3) and benzyl alcohol (4) as the main products. In the presence of a little water, however, phenyl benzyl selenoxide (2a) was formed in 54% yield. Thus, water was found to be required for the formation of selenoxide (2a) in the reaction of selenide (1a) with TTFA. (Scheme 1)

In the reaction of sulfide with TTN, the formation of a cation radical through a one electron oxidation was recognized by its esr spectrum¹. Also in the case of the similar reaction with the selenide, the formation of a cation radical was shown. Thus the short-lived cation radical ($g=2.0210 \pm 0.0005$) was detected by esr technique, when it was measured for a solution of di(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-selenide (1c) and TTN in dimethoxyethane in a degassed tube at -60°C.

TABLE

REACTION OF SELENIDES WITH TTN^a

Selenide (1)	Solvent	Reaction time	Yield (%) ^b of the corresponding selenoxide (2)
C ₆ H ₅ SeCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅ (1a)	THF	20 min	87 (2a)
..	HC(OMe) ₃	5 min	98 (2a)
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ Se (1b)	THF	24 hr	92 (2b)
(<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄) ₂ Se (1c)	THF	2 hr	100 (2c)

^a In all cases, 1.5 mol equivalents of TTN were used.
^b Isolated yield.

In the reaction of phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) with TTFA under the presence of water, the nucleophilic attack of water to the initially formed cation radical (5) may occur to give selenoxide (2a), but in the absence of water the cation radical probably decomposes into phenyl selenium radical (6) and benzyl cation (7), and they may change to diphenyl diselenide (3), and benzyl alcohol (4), respectively (Scheme 2).

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken with a micro hot-stage apparatus. IR spectra were recorded with a Hitachi EPI-S2 spectrometer and NMR spectra with a Varian T-60 spectrometer for solutions in [²H] chloroform (tetramethylsilane as internal standard). Mass spectra were determined with a JEOL JMS-01SG double-focusing spectrometer. Extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄.

Oxidation of selenides with TTN.

a) *Phenyl benzyl selenoxides (2a)*: In *Tetrahydrofuran*.—To a solution of phenyl benzyl selenide (1a)⁹ (92 mg), which was prepared by the reaction of diphenyl diselenide and benzyl chloride, in tetrahydrofuran (2 ml) was added TTN (247 mg). Immediately the solution coloured to brown. After stirring for 20 min, the mixture was chromatographed on alumina [W 200 basic (Woelm), grade II]. Elution with methylene chloride recovered the starting material (3 mg). Elution with methylene chloride-methanol (85 : 15) gave crystalline phenyl benzyl selenoxide (2a) (85 mg, 87% yield) as colourless plates (from benzene), m.p. 135-136° (*lit.*,⁶ m.p. 135-136°). IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ s. 3300, 825, and 690 cm⁻¹. NMR δ : 3.93 and 4.13 (each 1H, AB type, $J=12\text{Hz}$).

In *trimethyl orthoformate*.—After stirring the solution of TTN (135 mg) in trimethyl orthoformate (2 ml) for 1 hr, phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) (50 mg) was added to this solution. Stirring was continued for 5 min, then the solvent was evaporated off *in vacuo* to give a residue, which was chromatographed as above to afford (2a) (52 mg, 98% yield).

b) *Diphenyl selenoxide (2b)*.—To a solution of diphenyl selenide (1b)¹⁰ (55 mg), which was prepared from diphenyl diselenide and phenylmagnesium bromide, in tetrahydrofuran (1.5 ml) was added TTN (157 mg). After stirring for 24 hr, the mixture was chromatographed on alumina. Elution with n-hexane recovered the starting material (4 mg). Elution with methylene chloride-methanol (9 : 1) gave diphenyl selenoxide (2b) (54 mg, 92% yield), m.p. 110-111° (from benzene) and dried at 105° under vacuum (*lit.*,¹¹ m.p. 112.8°). IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ s. 3300, 1445, 825, and 685 cm⁻¹. NMR δ : 7.37-7.83. mass spectrum m/e : 250 (M⁺), 234 (M⁺-O), and 77 (C₆H₅).

c) *Di(p-methoxyphenyl)-selenoxide (2c)*.—To a solution of di(p-methoxyphenyl)-selenide(1c)¹² (110 mg), which was prepared from anisol and selenium dioxide, in tetrahydrofuran (3 ml) was added TTN (250 mg). After stirring for 2 hr, the mixture was chromatographed to give di(p-methoxyphenyl)-selenoxide (2c) (116 mg), m.p. 142-143° (*lit.*,⁴ m.p. 144°). IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ s. 3300, 1495, 1255, and 830 cm⁻¹. NMR δ : 3.77 (6H, s, -OCH₃).

Oxidation of phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) with TTFA

a) *In the Absence of Water*.—TTFA (2.861 g) was dissolved in trifluoroacetic acid (6 ml) under N₂ in dry box. To this solution was added phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) (808 mg), and the solution was stirred for 2 hr. After the addition of small amount of water, the mixture was extracted with chloroform. Usual treatment of the extract left an oily residue, which was chromatographed on alumina. Elution with methylene chloride afforded an oily mixture (508 mg). Preparative TLC of one tenth of the mixture developed with n-hexane gave two compounds. The compound with larger R_f value was diphenyl diselenide (3) (29 mg), m.p. 62°. The compound with smaller R_f value was the starting material (12 mg). Elution with methylene chloride-methanol (9 : 1) gave benzyl alcohol (4) (181 mg).

b) *In the presence of water*.—To a solution of phenyl benzyl selenide (1a) (72 mg) in trifluoroacetic acid (1.5 ml) and water (0.25 ml) was added TTFA (238 mg). After stirring for 2 hr, the solvent was evaporated off under reduced pressure to leave an oil, which was chromatographed on alumina. Elution with methylene chloride recovered the starting material (8 mg). Elution with methylene chloride-methanol (9 : 1) yielded phenyl benzyl selenoxide (2a) (41 mg, 54%).

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References

1. Preliminary communication: Y. NAGAO, M. OCHIAI, K. KANEKO, A. MAEDA, K. WATANABE and E. FUJITA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1977, 1345.
2. P. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3533; T.-L. HO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 75, 1.
3. A. MCKILLOP and E. C. TAYLOR, *Chem. in Britain*, 1973, 9, 4, and references cited therein.
4. E. S. GOULD and J. D. MCCULLOUGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3196.
5. G. AYREY, D. BARNARD and D. T. WOODBRIDGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2089.
6. M. CINQUINI, S. COLONNA and R. GIOVINI, *Chem. and Ind. (London)*, 1969, 1737.
7. H. J. REICH and S. K. SHAH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 97, 3250.
8. L. HEVESI and A. KRIEF, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1976, 15, 381.
9. O. BEHAGHEL and K. HOFMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1939, 72, 697.
10. T. W. CAMPBELL and J. D. MCCULLOUGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1965.
11. H. RHEINBOLDT and E. GIESBRECHT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2671.
12. G. V. BOYD, M. DOUGHTY and J. KENYON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2196.